

Appendix A Specification Document

Field	Value
Domain	Cultural heritage
Date	February 2nd, 2025
Conceptualized By	Christian D. H. Nababan
Implemented By	Christian D. H. Nababan
Level of Formality	Formal (OWL DL)
Scope	Glossary Terms
Concepts	Outreach, Activity, Discussion, Protocol, Mistake, Information, Label, Community, Rule, Condition, Specific Use, Incomplete, Attribution, Author, Education, Research, DSI, Data, Knowledge, Traditional, Membership, Sensitive, Colonialism, Creative Practice, Individual, Copyright, Relationship, Provenance, Authorized, Material, Men, Women, Gender, Period, External, Important, Secret, Sacred, User, External, Third Party, Authorized, Others, Outside, Value, Expectation, Restricted, Customary Law, Expression, Care, Derogatory, Error, Treatment, Use, Circulation, Access, Misunderstanding, Free, Public, Available, Significance, Commercialization, Exchange, Opportunity, Interest, Negotiation, Primary, Subject, Text, Clan, Family, Viewers, Culture, Internal, Relation, Collection, Consent, Place, Process, Creation, Accuracy, Representation, Engagement, Unspecified, Geography, Purpose, Collaboration, Partnership, Narrative, Multiplicity, Story, Voice, Existing, History, Description, Event, Recording, Photograph, Heritage Item, Practice, Collective, Respect, Land, Teaching, Ceremony, Context, Download, Open, Copy, Custodian, Holder, Awareness, Group, Possibility, Circumstance, Reciprocal Exchange, Interconnected, Rights, Specific Share, Resource
Verbs	Apply, ask, communicate, connect, comprise, contain, demand, share, group, have, access, restricts, notify, recognize, use, specify, circulate, verify, discuss, attribute, associate, derived, owned, clarify, acknowledge, respect, consider, treat, include, require, inform, designate, consent, provide, allow, support, encourage, tell, listen, reclaim, invite, satisfy, represent, influence, impact, utilize, correct, increase, convey, embody, retain, name, affirm, reflect, vet, emerge, download, copy
Source	Traditional Knowledge Label Official Documents 2025 Version